

Tentative project title

Evaluating the Prognostic Value of Hemoglobin/Creatinine Ratio in Predicting All-Cause Mortality and Cardiovascular risk

Authors

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Aim

To examine the prognostic values of hemoglobin/creatinine, ratio in the general population. We hypothesize that hemoglobin to creatinine ratio provides a better prognostic marker than hemoglobin or creatinine alone.

Materials and methods

To **determine** the prognostic values of hemoglobin, creatinine and hemoglobin/creatinine-ratio in the general population, a prospective cohort study will be performed on the DANCAVAS cohort intervention group [1]. The DANCAVAS intervention group consists of approximately 15.000 Danish citizens of the age 65-74 years who were randomly invited to undergo cardiovascular screening. DANCAVAS includes extensive data such as blood samples at baseline, questionnaires, medical history, diagnose codes and medications from electronic medical records.

The explanatory variables of interest (hemoglobin/creatinine ratio, hemoglobin and creatinine) were measured at baseline as part of the screening intervention in the DANCAVAS intervention group. Information regarding medication will be gathered within the period of a year prior to medication to one-year follow-up. Prescribed medications will be grouped according to ATC codes (supplementary table 1).

The primary outcome of the study will be all-cause mortality within one year of follow-up. The secondary outcomes will be 5-year survival, major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) or cardiovascular death within one year of follow-up, defined as either, onset of or death from acute myocardial infarction, stroke, major adverse lower leg event defined as either revascularization or amputation of any part of the leg except only toes. Secondary outcome variables will be based on registered diagnose codes (supplementary table 2).

Statistical analysis

All analysis will be performed in R (4.5.1).

Descriptive

Continuous variables will be presented as mean and standard deviation if they are approximately normally distributed. Normality and symmetry will be assessed with histograms and Q-Q plots, as to not rely solely on formal tests due to the sensitivity of sample size. Non-normal continuous variables will be presented as median with interquartile range. Normally distributed data will be further analyzed with unpaired t-test for differences between the groups. Non-normally distributed data will be tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Categorical variables will be presented as n(%) and will be tested with chi-squared or Fishers exact test if any expected cell count is less than five.

Logistical regression

We will evaluate the predictive values of explanatory variables of interest with multivariable logistic regression models. The final number of explanatory variables included will depend on the number of events of primary and secondary outcomes. For every 10 events a covariate will be included in the model [2] in the following order:

1. Explanatory variable of interest: hemoglobin, creatinine or hemoglobin/creatinine
2. Age (years)
3. Biological sex (Female/Male)
4. Smoking (yes/no)
5. Von Walraven summary score of the Elixhauser comorbidity index, using the R package “comorbidity”
6. treatment with angiotensin-converting Enzyme inhibitors or Angiotensin-II receptor blockers (yes/no)
7. antithrombotic agents (yes/no) (anticoagulants or platelet inhibitors)
8. nutrition replenishment therapy (yes/no) (B12, folate, iron supplements)
9. prescribed erythropoietin or Hypoxia-inducible factor prolyl hydroxylase inhibitors
10. prescribed non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs (yes/no)
11. prescribed sodium-glucose cotransporter inhibitors (yes/no)
12. prescribed blood pressure medication other than angiotensin-converting Enzyme inhibitors or Angiotensin-II receptor blockers, in the classes of beta blocking agents, calcium channel blockers, diuretics and other antihypertensive agents (yes/no)
13. prescribed lipid-lowering therapy in the classes of HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, fibrates, bile acid sequestrants, nicotinic acids or other lipid lowering agents (yes/no)

We will assess model multicollinearity with Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Variables with a VIF of >5 will be reevaluated. Linearity between the outcome logit and continuous explanatory variable will be assessed with the Box-Tidwell test – if not linear, the explanatory variable is removed from the model. Finally, we will assess goodness of fit with the Hosmer-Lemeshow test.

To evaluate the predictive values of the explanatory variables of interest, we will compare Area under the curve (AUC) of Receiver operating characteristics of each model. AUC will be

calculated with/without explanatory variables of interest. Differences between AUC of each model will be compared with DeLong's test. The quantity of increase in AUC will guide the interpretation of the predictive value of each explanatory variable of interest. A significant increase in AUC compared to the model not including the explanatory variable of interest will be interpreted as added predictive value. Larger significant increases in AUC depending on added explanatory variable of interest will determine which explanatory variable of interest provides the largest predictive value.

Outlines of expected Tables

Table 1: baseline statistics of included participants

Variable	Statistic

Table 2: descriptive analysis, difference in those with outcome vs those without outcome, primary outcome

Variable	Event	Non-event	Statistic

Table 3: descriptive analysis, difference in those with outcome vs those without outcome, secondary outcome

Variable	Event	Non-event	Statistic

Table 4: Logistical regression analysis performance depending on exposure variable of interest vs other vs covariates only, primary outcome

Exposure variable of interest	Odds ratio (95 % confidence interval)	P-value	Area under the curve
Hemoglobin/creatinine			
Hemoglobin			
Creatinine			
None of the above	-	-	

Table 5: Logistical regression analysis performance depending on exposure variable of interest vs other vs covariates only, secondary outcome

Exposure variable of interest	Odds ratio (95 % confidence interval)	P-value	Area under the curve
Hemoglobin/creatinine			
Hemoglobin			
Creatinine			
None of the above	-	-	

Outlines of expected supplementary tables

Supplementary table 1 – table of ATC codes used for data extraction and analysis

ATC Code	Main Group (Therapeutic Class)	Description (Subgroup/Specific Agents)
C09	<u>AGENTS ACTING ON THE RENIN-ANGIOTENSIN SYSTEM</u>	
C09AA		ACE inhibitors, plain
C09BA		ACE inhibitors and diuretics in combination
C09CA		Angiotensin II antagonists, plain
C09DA		Angiotensin II antagonists and diuretics in combination
B01A	<u>ANTITHROMBOTIC AGENTS</u>	
B01AA		Vitamin K antagonists
B01AB		Heparin group
B01AC		Platelet aggregation inhibitors excluding heparin
B01AE		Direct thrombin inhibitors
B01AF		Direct factor Xa inhibitors
B03	<u>ANTIANEMIC PREPARATIONS</u>	
B03A	<u>IRON PREPARATIONS</u>	
B03AA and B03AB		Bivalent iron and trivalent iron, oral preparation
B03AC		Iron, parenteral preparation
B03B	<u>VITAMIN B12 AND FOLIC ACID</u>	
B03BA		Vitamin B12 (cyanocobalamins and analogues)
B03BB		Folic acid and derivatives
B03XA		Erythropoitins and HIF-PHIs

M01A	<u>ANTIINFLAMMATORY AND ANTIRHEUMATIC PRODUCTS, NON-STEROIDS</u>	
A10BK	<u>Sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors</u>	
	<u>OTHER ANTIHYPERTENSIVES</u>	
C02C		Alpha-blocking agents 1
C08C		Dihydropyridine derivatives
C08D		Non-dihydropyridine derivatives
C07A		Beta-blocking agents
C07C		Beta-blocking agents and diuretics in combination
C07B		Beta-blocking agents and thiazides in combination
C03	<u>DIURETICS</u>	
C10A	<u>LIPID MODIFYING AGENTS, PLAIN</u>	
C10AA		HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors
C10AB		Fibrates
C10AC		Bile acid sequestrants (Anion exchangers)
C10AD		Nicotinic acid and derivatives
C10AX		Other lipid modifying agents
C10B	<u>LIPID MODIFYING AGENTS, COMBINATIONS</u>	
C10BA		Combinations of various lipid modifying agents
C10BX		Lipid modifying agents in combination with other drugs

Supplementary table 2 – ICD-10 diagnoses codes used as definitions of the secondary outcome

ICD-10 code	Diagnosis	Sub-category
I21	Acute myocardial infarction	
I21.0		Acute transmural myocardial infarction of anterior wall
I21.1		Acute transmural myocardial infarction of inferior wall
I21.2		Acute transmural myocardial infarction of other sites
I21.3		Acute transmural myocardial infarction of unspecified site
I21.4		Acute subendocardial myocardial infarction
I21.9		Acute myocardial infarction, unspecified
I20	Unstable angia	
I20.1		Angina pectoris with documented spasms
I20.8		Other forms of angina pectoris
I20.9		Angina pectoris, unspecified
I63	Cerebral infarction	
I63.0		Cerebral infarction due to thrombosis of precerebral arteries
I63.1		Cerebral infarction due to embolism of precerebral arteries
I63.2		Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of precerebral arteries
I63.3		Cerebral infarction due to thrombosis of cerebral arteries
I63.4		Cerebral infarction due to embolism of cerebral arteries
I63.5		Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of cerebral arteries
I63.6		Cerebral infarction due to cerebral venous thrombosis, nonpyogenic

I63.8		Other cerebral infarction
I63.9		Cerebral infarction, unspecified
I74	Arterial embolism and thrombosis	
I74.0		Embolism and thrombosis of abdominal aorta (aortic bifurcation syndrome or Leriche syndrome)
I74.1		Embolism and thrombosis of other and unspecified parts of aorta
I74.2		Embolism and thrombosis of arteries of upper extremities
I74.3		Embolism and thrombosis of arteries of lower extremities
I74.4		Embolism and thrombosis of arteries of extremities, unspecified
I74.5		Embolism and thrombosis of iliac artery
I74.8		Embolism and thrombosis of other arteries
I74.9		Embolism and thrombosis of unspecified artery
Z89	Acquired absence of limb	
Z89.4		Acquired absence of foot and ankle Toe(s)
Z89.5		Acquired absence of leg at or below knee
Z89.6		Acquired absence of leg above knee

SKS-codes for surgical elements of MALE

Type of operation	SKS-code
Bypass surgery from infrarenal aorta and iliac arteries	KPDH
Percutaneous surgery on infrarenal aorta and iliac arteries	KPDP
Thrombendarterectomies of the femoral artery and its arterial branches	KPEF
Axilloiliacal bypass operation	KPGH20
Axillobiliaical bypass operation	KPGH21
Axillofemoral bypass operation	KPGH22
Axillobifemoral bypass operation	KPGH23
Iliacofemoral contralateral bypass operation	KPGH30
Iliacofemoral contralateral bypass operation accessed from foramen obturatum	KPGH31
Thrombectomies or embolectomies of the femoral artery and its arterial branches	KPEE
Bypass surgery on the femoral artery and its arterial branches	KPEH
Percutaneous angioplasty on the femoral artery or its branches	KPEP
Thrombectomies or embolectomies of the popliteal artery and its arterial branches	KPFE
Bypass surgery on the popliteal artery and its arterial branches	KPFH
Percutaneous angioplasty on the popliteal artery or its branches	KPFP
Trans-Femoral Amputation	KNFQ19, KNFQ99
Hip Exarticulation	KNFQ09
Trans-Tibial Amputation (Through the lower leg bones)	KNGQ19, KNGQ99
Knee Disarticulation	KNGQ09

SKS-codes for surgical elements of MACE

Type operation	SKS-code
CAB by use of free arterial graft	KFNE00-20
Expansion and recanalization of coronary arteries, including percutaneous approaches	KFNG

References

1. Lindholt, J.S., et al., *Five-Year Outcomes of the Danish Cardiovascular Screening (DANCAVAS) Trial*. N Engl J Med, 2022. **387**(15): p. 1385-1394.
2. Peduzzi, P., et al., *A simulation study of the number of events per variable in logistic regression analysis*. J Clin Epidemiol, 1996. **49**(12): p. 1373-9.